

Working Capital Management at Suzlon Energy Ltd. Pune

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ABSTRACT:

For a successful working of a business organization fixed and current assets play a vital role Management of working capital is essential as it has direct impact on profitability and liquidity. An attempt has been made in this paper to study the working capital components and impact of working capital management on profitability in “SUZLON ENERGY LTD” COMPANY. The study is based on secondary data collected from annual reports of Suzlon Energy LTD. This project report basically based on Working capital Management. Through this project we can understand the working capital management in Suzlon Energy Ltd.

Keywords: Working Capital Management, Current asset, Current liability, Account receivable, Account payable

I. INTRODUCTION:

Working capital Management: Management of working capital of an organization is very important as it will decide the amount of current asset and current liability that are to be mention in business. The amount of working capital set the various policies in business like purchasing, general operation, financing expansion, and dividend. It shows the liquidity position of the business for the management of short term asset and liability. Company's current asset are more than current liability that Time Company has enough amount of fund for day to day operation and also satisfy short term depth.

1.2 FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

Suzlon Energy Ltd is Wind Turbine and solar power based company in Pune, It was once in the past positioned by make as the world 5 biggest breeze turbine provider It has since dropped out of the Global top 10 rankings starting at 2014 because of broad misfortunes and powerlessness to re-pay obligations. The organization's site professes to have over 17,000MW of wind vitality limit introduced all around, with tasks

crosswise over 18 nations, workforce of more than 8,000. If defiance of financial issues, in 2016 continues be a major manufacturer of wind turbines, the company posted a benefit EBITDA accumulating misfortunes more than seven sequential years. Due to globalization & too much dependency over technology has created huge reliability over electricity causing lot of pollution & costs as well as most of electricity is produced from burning fossil fuels & in terms is not green fuel. Due to limited availability of this non-green fuel has created gap between demand & supply of required electricity by humans. To bridge these gap renewable energy resources such as Sun, Wind, etc. can be utilized. Also, these are green fuel resources & hence does not cause any harm to environment along with production of mankind. Thus, these are long life sustainable energy resources if utilized in proper manner.

1.3 NEED FOR THE STUDY

Working capital means a portion of the total fund which are required for financing day to day operation in the organization. Working capital required for continuity in production, distribution to society. The company need working capital for the financing current asset of the company like inventory, debtors, cash in hand and bank, short term loan and advances and payment of tax and so on.

WORKING CAPITAL = CURRENT ASSET- CURRENT LIABILITIES

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To Evaluation of working capital management
2. To study the various kind of components of current asset and current liability.
3. To study the financial strength and weaknesses of the Suzlon Energy LTD.
4. To analyze the financial position of the company for the last three years.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Researchers also need to understand the belief under various typographical they need to know the benchmark by which they decide that certain technique and procedure will be applicable to a certain problems will not. This implies it is essential for the scientist to structure his procedure for his concern as the equivalent may adjust from issue to issue.

2.2 SOURCES OF DATA

Secondary data use for the study, collected from the Suzlon. The data for the above study has been collected through secondary data. Here various types of variables for the test link between working capital management and profitability of the organization

- Annual report of the Suzlon Energy LTD. For the last three year.
- Official website of Suzlon Energy LTD. www.suzlon.com

2.3 PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The present examination spread a time of three years from 2017-2019

2.4 FRAME WORK OF ANALYSIS

The company's performance can be done finished a carefully and critical analysis of financial statements. The 2 significant fiscal reports are Balance sheet and Profit and misfortune account. It indicates the operating results and financial position of the involvement; in this manner by investigating the announcements, execution can be advised.

2.5 LIMITATIONS

1. Time is to be one of the measure limitations.
2. Frequently change in the company's financial decision.
3. The study is based on the past data and may not be true indicator of future performance due to changes in the various fundamental as well as other aspects.

III. Management of working capital

Working capital is related to the current asset and current liability of the organization. Any problem that happens with working capital that time only manages the current asset and current liability for the satisfying level of the working capital of the organization. The working capital level should not excessive and lower both situations are bad for the organization. There should not shortage of fund and working capital should not be idle. WORKING CAPITAL POLICY of the firm is grate that time profitability, liquidity, structural health of the organization should be in a good position.

➤ There are three dimensions of working capital management.

1. It concerned with the formulation of the policy regarding profitability, liquidity and risk.
2. It concerned with the decision about the composition and level of the current asset.

3. It concerned with the decision about the composition and level of the current liability.

IV. PROFITABILITY RATIOS:

Ratio: - It is the Ratio of total current asset to total Current liability the current ration of a company measurement its Short- term solvency.

1. Current ratio formula: - Current ratio = Current asset/Current liability

Table No-1

Year	Current Asset	Current Liability	Current ratio
2019	65,143	109,492	0.50
2018	85,110	101,558	0.83
2017	91705	137591	0.66

GRAPH NO:-1

Interpretation: -

Companies Current ratio is not better than it is ideal level but if see last 3years Current ratio of Company. It has incise from 2017-19 the Current ratio of organization is close to perfect proportion is detail that organizations liquidity position is vastly improved. Current Assets are more than Current Liabilities

2. Net Profit Margin ratio:-

Net Profit Margin ratio= Net Income/Revenue

Table: - 2

Year	Net Income	Revenue	Ration
2019	15272	50247	0.30
2018	3928	83338	0.04
2017	9548	127144	0.07

GRAPH NO:-2

Interpretation: -

Net Profit Margin ratio is not better than it is ideal level but if see last 3 years Net Profit Margin ratio of Company. It has incise from 2017-19. It has incise from 2017-19 the Net Profit Margin ratio of company is near to ideal ratio depicts that companies liquidity position is much better. Its Revenue are more than Net Income

3. Free cash flow Ratio: -

Free Cash flow Ratio = Cash flow Operation – Capital Expenditure

Table No. 3

Year	Cash flow Operation	capital Expenditure	Ration
2019	11192	2727.52	8464.48
2018	-8050	5502.26	-13552.26
2017	16088	7410.52	8677.48

GRAPH NO:-3

Interpretation: -

Free cash flow Ratio is not better than ideal level but if we see the free cash flow Ratio of company for last 3 years. It has increase and decrease from 2017-19 the Free cash flow Ratio of company is close to perfect proportion is delineates that organization's liquidity position is vastly improved. In that case 2017 Cash Flow are more than Capital Expenditure, 2018 Capital Expenditure are more than Cash Flow, 2019 Cash Flow are more than Capital Expenditure.

4. Interest Coverage Ratio:-

Interest Coverage Ratio= Interest Coverage Ratio= Operation Income/ Interest

Table: - 4

Year	Operation Income	Interest	Ratio
2019	-15272	-12699	1.20
2018	-3928	-15810	0.24
2017	9548	-12876	0.74

GRAPH NO:-4

Interpretation: -

Interest Coverage Ratio is not better than its ideal level but if we see the Interest Coverage Ratio of company for last three years. It has incise and decrease from 2017-19 the Interest Coverage Ratio of company is near to ideal ratio is depicts that company's liquidity position is vastly improved. In that case 2017 Operation Income are more than Interest, 2018 Operation Income and Interest both are Loss or Less, 2019 Operation Income and Interest both are Loss Or Less,

V. FINDINGS

1. In 2019 Current Ratio is decrease but impervious year Current ratio is Increase.
2. The non-Current Assets are decrease in the year 2017-2019.
3. Net profit margin is increase in the year 2017-2019.
4. Cash flow is 2019 and 2017 are increase and 2018 Cash flow is decrease.
5. Interest coverage ratio of 2017 is increase and 2018 as well as 2019 Interest coverage ratio id decrease.
6. The assets are decrease during the period of study.

VI. CONCLUSION:

If you want to understand or reviewer a company's cash flow strength to look management of working capital of any organization.

Working capital management was very important to any organization. Organizations have a lot of challenges in maintaining working capital like credit management. The organization have to improve in all sector for the development of organization working capital is one of them.

This dissertation project gave me real time work experience. The project indirectly help me to learn working capital, developed me, take initiative and ability to solve the problems.

VII. BIBLIOGRAPHY:

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